

TOUGHNESS MODIFICATION OF PLA BASED BLENDS WITH NANOCRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE

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Abstract: *The main objective of packaging material is to protect the contents. Glass, paper, cardboard and plastic have become very important packaging materials. From the 1970s, the plastic packaging sector began to grow. Due to the large amount of plastic waste in the environment, consumers demanded the development of environmentally friendly packaging materials. Polylactic acid (PLA) is one of the bio-based and biodegradable alternatives. Besides good processing properties, PLA also has some drawbacks. The most pronounced one for use in the packaging sector is brittleness. To avoid this drawback, nanocrystalline cellulose (NCC) can be incorporated into the PLA matrix. To prevent the agglomeration of NCC and improve the surface interaction between NCC and PLA, the surface modification of NCC is the most researched topic. For packaging material, price is also an extremely important issue. Surface modification of NCC is an additional processing step that also involves chemicals and is not always environmentally friendly. An alternative to surface modification of NCC is the use of a suitable compatibilizer to improve the surface interactions between NCC and the thermoplastic matrix and to allow uniform dispersion and distribution of NCC in the thermoplastic matrix. Three different concentrations of surface unmodified NCC (1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, and 5 wt.%) in PLA-based blends were prepared. A PLA-based blend without NCC was used as a reference. Two compounding cycles were performed to investigate the effect of shearing during processing on the properties of the nanocomposites and the distribution of NCC in the thermoplastic matrix. The addition of NCC increases the stiffness, strength and elongation at break. The glass transition temperatures are not affected by the addition of NCC.*

Moreover, the NCC prevents the crystallization of the PLA matrix upon cooling and postpones the cold crystallization of the PLA matrix upon heating to higher temperatures. The toughness was improved in the nanocomposites with NCC. The results show that the toughness of the PLA blend was improved by the addition of NCC, although NCC was used without surface modification. Modification with a suitable compatibilizer during compounding is the environmentally friendly alternative for the production of nanocomposites for the packaging industry.

Keywords: PLA, NCC, toughness modification, compatibilizer

1 INTRODUCTION

Commercially available biodegradable PLA is the first choice as a solution for the circular economy in many sectors, including packaging. The main obstacle for PLA is its brittleness. To overcome PLA's brittle behavior, scientists have done a lot of research. The toughness of PLA has been improved through various strategies, including plasticization, copolymerization, and melt blending with various tough polymers, rubbers, and thermoplastic elastomers. Due to the lack of reactive side groups, modification of PLA is a difficult process. The toughness of PLA can be compared to the toughness of polystyrene, which is commonly used in the packaging sector. The toughness depends on the molecular weight, the spatial arrangement of the molecules, the degree of crystallinity and the miscibility in the case of thermoplastic blends. To assess the brittleness of the material, tensile tests (elongation at break) and impact tests are most commonly used. The most effective toughening process remains tensile stiffness and tensile strength (Krishnan et al., 2016). For neat PLA, the influence of increasing degree of crystallinity of semi-crystalline PLA on toughness improvement has been reported (Anderson et al., 2008). The most effective ways to orient the PLA molecule are pulling and biaxial orientation. Blending with plasticizers increases the elasticity and drastically decreases the strength of the compounds. With the modification of the bulk and surface, the application range of PLA is expanding (Rasal et al., 2010). Recent bulk modifications of PLA to achieve a tough PLA reduce stiffness and strength and also lose toughness with physical aging. Surface modification of PLA with reactive and non-reactive groups can also affect the properties of bulk PLA as monomers from the surface modification groups migrate into the bulk PLA. It has been reported that the toughness of PLA is increased by melt blending with thermoplastic tougheners and reactive blending (Liu & Zhang, 2011).

The addition of non-biodegradable petroleum-based thermoplastic material in excess of 20 wt.% resulted in higher impact strength, but at the same time stiffness and strength decreased rapidly. The relationship between the toughness of PLA and the degree of crystallization has not yet been clarified. The thermodynamic immiscibility of PLA with most thermoplastics leads to unexpected high-performance PLA-based blends (Zeng et al., 2015). To avoid this weakness, compatibilization is required in melt blending. The addition of copolymers is the conventional and efficient way to achieve compatibilized polymer blends. The main obstacle is the lack of commercially available PLA copolymers. Reactive compatibilization is also applicable in industrial applications. The incorporation of nanoparticles in reactive compatibilization can further improve the mechanical properties and toughness due to the reinforcing effect of nanoparticles by changing interfacial properties and phase morphologies. Functionalized organoclay (Chen et al., 2005; Risse et al., 2014) affects the morphology of PLA/PBS blends due to the compatibilization effect of nanoparticles. Organoclay acts as a compatibilizer in PLA/PCL blends (Hoidy et al., 2010), PLA/PBSA blends (Ojijo et al., 2012) and PLA/TPS blends (Ferreira et al., 2015). The compatibility of PLA/PCL blends was improved by the addition of functionalized multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (Wu et al., 2009).

The functionalized MWCNTs were mainly dispersed in PCL and at the phase interface. The addition of modified polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxane (POSS) (Monticelli et al., 2014) allows the formation of a homogeneous microstructure in the PLA/PCL blend. A PLA/PC blend with nano-silica (Irani-Kolash et al., 2020) with a suitable compatibilizer is a promising environmentally friendly material. Lower stiffness and strength with higher elongation at break were characterized. Samarium acetylacetonate (Chelghoum et al., 2018) facilitates transesterification reactions between PLA and PC and improves the performance of PLA/PC blend. The compatibilizer helped promote a significant enhancement effect as evidenced by the increase in storage modulus of the blend in the temperature interval between the end and the beginning of PLA glass transition or cold crystallization. Surface-modified nanocrystalline cellulose nanocomposites in PLA/PBS blends improved interfacial adhesion, stiffness while reducing strength and elongation at break (Kian et al., 2019). Addition of 1 wt.% NCC to PLA matrix increased the stiffness, but addition of 2 wt.% and 3 wt.% decreased the stiffness compared to neat PLA matrix (Sullivan et al., 2015). Different effects of the added amount of NCC were reported (Sung et al., 2017), where the addition of 1 wt.%, 3 wt.% and 5 wt.% increased the stiffness of the nanocomposites with PLA matrix compared to the neat PLA matrix. The elongation at break increased with NCC addition of 1 wt.% and decreased with NCC addition of 3 wt.% and 5 wt.% into the PLA matrix. All reported results for

NCC were obtained with surface modified NCC. The wet blend (Sabo et al., 2019) of NCC and PLA showed improved barrier and mechanical properties.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2. 1 Sample

Commercially available PLA with the trade name Ingeo 4043D was provided by Plastika Trček, Slovenia. Commercially available polycarbonate with the trade name Lexan 243 R was purchased from the company Sabic, Austria. NCC was donated by the company Navitas, Slovenia. Commercially available SEBS-g- MA with the trade name FG 1901 GT was purchased from the company Kraton, Germany. Commercially available TPU copolymer with trade name Kuramiron U TU -S5265 was purchased from Kuraray, Germany. Commercially available CaCO₃ with the trade name Calplex Extra was donated by the company Calcit, Slovenia. The composition of the samples is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of the samples and number of comounding cycles

Sample	PLA (wt.%)	PC (wt.%)	SEBS (wt.%)	TPU (wt.%)	CaCO₃ (wt.%)	NCC (wt.%)	Compounding cycles
<i>PLAPC</i>	42	40	10	5	3	0	1
<i>PLAPC 1NCC-1</i>	41	40	10	5	3	1	1
<i>PLAPC 1NCC-2</i>	41	40	10	5	3	1	2
<i>PLAPC 2NCC-1</i>	40	40	10	5	3	2	1
<i>PLAPC 2NCC-2</i>	40	40	10	5	3	2	2
<i>PLAPC 5NCC-1</i>	37	40	10	5	3	5	1
<i>PLAPC 5NCC-2</i>	37	40	10	5	3	5	2

2. 2 Processing

For the first compounding cycle, the materials were mixed separately and extruded on the Labtech LTE 20-44 twin screw extruder. The screws had a diameter of 20 mm, an L/D ratio of 44:1, a screw speed of 600 rpm, and an increasing temperature profile from the hopper (165 °C) to the die (200 °C). After compounding, the two produced filaments were cooled in a water bath and cut into pellets with a length of about 5 mm and a diameter of 3 mm. For the second compounding cycle, the prepared pellets of nanocomposites were extruded on the same extruder with identical extruder settings.

Injection molding was performed on Krauss Maffei 50-180 CX with a screw diameter of 30 mm. The temperature profile was increasing from the hopper (185 °C) to the die (200 °C). The mold temperature was set to 30 °C and the cooling time to 10 s. The back pressure was set to 150 bar and the screw speed to 50 rpm. The injection speed was set to 60 mm/s and to 20 mm/s for the last 1 mm.

2.3 Characterization

Flexural and tensile tests were performed on the Shimadzu AG -X plus according to ISO 178 and ISO 527-1, respectively. Five measurements were taken for each specimen. In the tensile tests, tensile stiffness (E_t), tensile strength (σ_m), elongation at yield (ϵ_m) and elongation at break (ϵ_{tb}) were determined. In the flexural tests, the flexural stiffness (E_f) and the flexural strength (σ_fM) and the elongation at yield (ϵ_fM) were evaluated. Thermomechanical properties were investigated using a Perkin Elmer DMA 8000. The specimens were heated at 2 °C/min from 25 °C to 180 °C under air atmosphere. A frequency of 1 Hz and an amplitude of 20 μ m in dual cantilever mode were used. Thermal measurements were performed using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC 2, Mettler Toledo) under nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min). The temperature of the samples was raised from 0 to 200 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min and held in the molten state for 5 min to erase their thermal history. After cooling at 10 °C/min, the samples were reheated to 200 °C at 10 °C/min. The crystallization temperature (T_c), crystallization enthalpy (ΔH_c), melting temperature (T_m), and melting enthalpy (ΔH_m) were determined from the cooling and the second heating scan. Oxidation induction time (OIT) measurements were determined using DSC 2 according to the standard method ISO 11357-6. After the sample was kept at 50 °C for 5 minutes under a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min, the timer started. The sample was heated from 50 °C to 200 °C at a rate of 20 °C/min and then held at a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min for 5 minutes to equilibrate. The gas was then switched to oxygen at a flow rate of 50 mL/min. Oxidation of the sample was observed as a sharp decrease in heat flux, which can be attributed to the endothermic nature of the oxidation reaction. The OIT was obtained as an on-set of the endothermic peak of the oxidation reaction. The cold crystallization behavior was determined on Mettler Toledo Flash DSC 1 with Huber intercooler TC45 and nitrogen purge gas (50 mL/min). The injection molded specimens were prepared from ISO 527 test specimens. Specimens were cooled from the melt (200 °C) to the desired temperature, rapidly heated to the aging temperature (90 °C for 100 s), rapidly cooled to 15 °C, reheated to 120 °C, and then cold crystallized at 120 °C for various times (from 0.1 s to 2,400 s). All cooling and heating segments were rapidly cooled and heated (500 °C/s) to prevent crystallization during cooling

and heating. The first heating run was performed from 15 °C to 200 °C. For the evaluation of the heating segment nr. 12 was taken and the melting temperature and enthalpy of fusion were characterized. The mass of the samples was determined with normalized specific heat capacity change in glass transition evaluation based on the evaluation of DSC-2 measurements. Impact tests were performed using the pendulum Dongguan Liyi Test Equipment, type LY -XJJD5, according to ISO 179. The distance between the supports was 60 mm, and a pendulum with 5 J and 1 J was used for the impact and notched impact tests, respectively.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties

Addition of NCC to a PLA-based blend improved strength, stiffness, and elongation at break (Figure 1) by adding 1 wt.% and one compounding cycle, as shown in Table 2. The additional compounding cycle decreased the flexural strength and stiffness, increased the tensile stiffness, and did not affect the tensile strength and elongation at break. At higher concentrations (2 wt.% and 5 wt.%) of NCC in PLA-based blends, the second compounding cycle lowers the strength and stiffness. Higher NCC loading results in lower flexural stiffness and higher tensile stiffness, strength and elongation at break, except for sample PLAPC 5NCC-2. Higher strength, stiffness and elongation at break are due to good compatibilization of NCC in PLA-based blend matrix and consequently good surface interaction of NCC and modified thermoplastics due to addition of compatibilizers SEBS and TPU. High shear value during compounding cycles and suitable compatibilizers prevent strong agglomeration of NCC in the PLA-based blends during processing, resulting in higher strength and elongation at break compared to neat PLA-based blends.

Table 2: Summarized results from the flexural and tensile tests

Sample	Flexural test results			Tensile test results			
	E_f (GPa)	σ_{fM} (MPa)	ϵ_{fM} (%)	E_t (GPa)	σ_m (MPa)	ϵ_m (%)	ϵ_{tb} (%)
PLAPC	2.03±0.02	48.2±1.1	3.13±0.28	2.17±0.16	31.6±0.3	3.5±0.3	4.8±0.6
PLAPC 1NCC-1	2.08±0.01	57.6±0.3	4.68±0.08	2.37±0.31	40.5±0.2	4.3±0.1	9.6±0.4
PLAPC 1NCC-2	2.02±0.01	55.6±0.3	4.71±0.06	2.44±0.24	40.7±0.4	4.5±0.2	9.5±0.8
PLAPC 2NCC-1	1.95±0.01	52.6±0.3	4.84±0.11	2.38±0.27	37.4±0.2	4.5±0.1	8.7±0.9
PLAPC 2NCC-2	1.88±0.01	51.1±0.2	4.86±0.14	2.33±0.11	37.3±0.4	4.3±0.1	8.8±1.0
PLAPC 5NCC-1	1.94±0.01	51.6±0.5	4.77±0.13	2.23±0.07	36.6±0.5	4.7±0.2	8.6±0.6
PLAPC 5NCC-2	1.81±0.01	40.4±2.4	3.00±0.49	2.01±0.13	31.5±0.6	3.9±0.1	4.6±0.3

Figure 1: Summarized results of the tensile strength (bars) and strain at break (line)

3. 2 Thermo-mechanical properties

The storage modulus curves (Figures 2 and 3) show the first drop at the glass transition temperature for PLA. The drop is more significant for PLA-based blends compared to PLA-based blends with NCC. The storage modulus is higher in this range (75 °C to 100 °C) with higher NCC content. Above 100 °C, the storage modulus increases due to cold crystallization of the material. The lowest peak for the cold crystallization temperature was for sample PLAPC (114 °C), and the highest peak was for sample PLAPC 1NCC-2 (119 °C). For all samples with NCC addition, the peak for cold crystallization temperature in the second compounding cycle was at a higher temperature than in the first compounding cycle. The addition of NCC to PLA-based blends inhibits the cold crystallization of PLA. At low NCC loading (1 wt.%), the NCC acts as a reinforcement for the PLA-based blend; at higher loadings (2 wt.% and 5 wt.%), the stiffness of the nanocomposites falls below the stiffness of the neat pure matrix. Despite the inhibitory effect of NCC on cold crystallization, the NCC prevents the softening of the PLA-based matrix after the glass transition temperature of PLA. The dissipation factor curve exhibits two sharp peaks at 69 °C and 160 °C (Figures 4 and 5), for the PLA and PC matrices, respectively. The height of the first peak is lowest for the PLAPC 1NCC sample and highest for the PLAPC sample. The height of the second peak is lowest for sample PLAPC and highest for sample PLAPC 1NCC. In the second compounding cycle,

the peak heights are higher, indicating the beginning of the degradation of the matrix. The most elastic behavior is exhibited by sample PLAPC 1NCC after the first compounding cycle. The good surface interaction of NCC with the matrix due to the compatibilizer in sample PLAPC 1NCC increases the storage modulus, maintains the storage modulus at a high level, and decreases the peak height of the loss factor for PLA. The higher peak of loss factor for PC in sample PLAPC 1NCC is due to the highest cold crystallization temperature in sample PLAPC 1NCC and consequently the overlap of the glass transition temperature of PC and the onset of melting of PLA.

Figure 2: Summarized results of storage modulus for the first compounding cycle

Figure 3: Summarized results of storage modulus for the second compounding cycle

Figure 4: Summarized results of loss factor for the first compounding cycle

Figure 5: Summarized results of loss factor for the second compounding cycle

3. 3 Thermal properties

The addition of NCC to PLA-based blends slightly shifts the glass transition temperature for PLA to higher temperatures, as do the cold crystallization temperatures and slightly melting temperatures (Table 3). The enthalpy of fusion is higher for NCC nanocomposites. The second compounding cycle lowers the glass transition and cold crystallization temperatures and increases the melting enthalpies without affecting the melting temperatures. With higher NCC content, the glass transition and melting temperatures as well as the melting enthalpies increase. The thermal stability is improved by the addition of NCC practically independent of the concentration and decreases with the second compounding cycle (Figure 6). The oxidation induction time and also the peak degradation time have the same trend. The crystallization kinetics were characterized by Flash DSC (Figures 7, 8). The onset of crystal moieties formation was after aging at 90 °C for 100 s and at 120 °C after 100 s for all samples. The shorter time is not sufficient for crystal moieties formation. Higher NCC loading promoted the formation of crystal moieties as well as the second compounding cycle. The fastest and largest increase in crystal moieties was for sample PLAPC 5NCC-2 up to the cold crystallization time 600 s, then for sample PLAPC 1NCC-2. It can be concluded that NCC inhibits cold crystallization at shorter times and promotes cold crystallization at longer times at elevated temperatures. The mobility of PLA chains at elevated temperatures reaches a

threshold for the formation of crystal moieties after 600 s at 1 wt.% and 2 wt.% NCC loading. At the concentration of 5 wt.% NCC loading, 100 s is sufficient due to the higher amount of NCC particles in the matrix. From the results, it can also be concluded that agglomeration of NCC occurs to a lesser extent and increases with increasing NCC content.

Table 3: Summarized results from the 2nd heating from DSC tests

Sample	T_g (°C)	ΔC_p (J/gK)	T_{cc} (°C)	ΔH_{cc} (J/g)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	Diff. ΔH_m (J/g)
PLAPC	59.8	0.106	123.6	5.35	152.0	5.37	0.02
PLAPC 1NCC-1	60.8	0.091	133.3	0.32	152.2	0.37	0.05
PLAPC 1NCC-2	60.6	0.094	128.3	0.04	152.2	0.33	0.29
PLAPC 2NCC-1	61.1	0.079	133.4	0.13	152.4	0.31	0.18
PLAPC 2NCC-2	60.7	0.085	131.6	0.18	152.8	0.52	0.34
PLAPC 5NCC-1	61.1	0.060	130.4	0.24	153.2	0.48	0.24
PLAPC 5NCC-2	60.1	0.078	128.4	1.28	152.9	1.67	0.39

Figure 6: Summarized results of oxidation induction time: onset time (bars) and peak time (line)

Figure 7: Summarized results of crystallization enthalpy of the samples after aging at 90 °C for 100 s and various cold crystallization times at 120 °C

Figure 8: Summarized results of melting temperature of the samples after aging at 90 °C for 100 s and various cold crystallization times at 120 °C

3. 4 Impact properties

The addition of NCC to a PLA-based blend increased the impact and notched impact strength. A higher amount of NCC and an additional compounding cycle lowered toughness. Higher impact and notched impact strength is achieved by good surface interaction between NCC and matrix. Lower toughness at higher concentrations of NCC in PLA-based blends is due to higher agglomeration of NCC. Lower toughness at second compounding cycle is due to slight degradation of thermoplastic matrix due to thermal degradation of PLA. The toughness of the nanocomposites is higher than that of the neat PLA-based blend except for the sample PLAPC 5NCC-2.

Figure 9: Summarized results of toughness: impact strength (bars) and notched impact strength (line)

4 CONCLUSION

The effect of adding NCC in three different ratios into PLA-based blends and in two compounding cycles on the toughness of nanocomposites NCC/PLA-based blends were investigated. The effect of incorporation of NCC into PLA-based blends and the mechanical and thermal properties were also studied.

Incorporation of unmodified NCC into PLA-based blends with TPU and SEBS compatibilizers at high shear during compounding greatly prevents

agglomeration of NCC and allows good surface interactions between NCC and thermoplastic matrix. The agglomeration of NCC was not reduced by the second compounding cycle, indicating a slight thermal degradation of PLA. The highest toughness of the nanocomposite was confirmed by the tensile test, where the addition of 1 wt.% NCC into a PLA-based blend increased the strength (+ 28%), stiffness (+ 9%), and elongation at break (+ 100%). The improvement in toughness was also confirmed by impact tests, which measured impact (+ 224 %) and notched impact (+ 32 %) strength compared to a PLA-only blend. Further increase of NCC addition and also the second compounding step lower the toughness, but the values are still higher compared to neat PLA blend. The addition of NCC inhibits the oxidation of nanocomposites, which is due to the higher thermal stability of nanocomposites due to the good surface interaction between NCC and the matrix. Second compounding steps decrease the oxidation induction time below the level of neat PLA blend. The addition of NCC to the PLA blend inhibits the cold crystallization of PLA under slow heating, but allows the formation of larger crystalline PLA moieties. The second compounding cycle leads to a slight degradation of the matrix and allows the formation of even larger crystalline PLA crystalline moieties due to shorter PLA chains.

Novel properties of PLA blends with NCC were developed by using appropriate compatibilizers during melt compatibilization. To describe the dependence on the amount of added NCC in nanocomposites, the addition of less than 1 wt.% NCC in PLA-based nanocomposite blends should be investigated in further research.

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